

Homology modeling, pharmacophore-guided virtual screening, molecular docking, and dynamics study of potential allosteric inhibitors targeting EGFR triple resistance mutations (L858R/T790M/L718Q)

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify potential allosteric inhibitors targeting the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) with the triple resistance mutations L858R, T790M, and L718Q through an integrated pharmacophore-guided virtual screening approach. Pharmacophore models were constructed based on the allosteric inhibitors EAI001 and EAI045, and their performance was evaluated using sensitivity and specificity parameters. The best-performing model (Model 4; sensitivity = 1, specificity = 0.92) was employed to screen the NCI Open Chemical Repository Database. Docking analyses were conducted against both the template and mutant EGFR structures using the Affinity dG scoring function with Alpha PMI placement. Toxicological profiles were predicted, and the stability of the selected complexes was assessed through 100 ns molecular dynamics simulations. Virtual screening identified 1,628 candidate compounds, and subsequent docking revealed 14 molecules with stronger binding affinities than the reference ligand. Among these, compound NSC3 demonstrated the highest affinity for both the template and mutant EGFR. Toxicological predictions indicated possible carcinogenicity, hepatotoxicity, and mutagenicity for some candidates. Molecular dynamics analyses showed that NSC3 exhibited greater conformational stability and hydrogen-bond persistence than EAI001. EAI001 displayed limited activity against the L718Q mutation, whereas NSC3 emerged as a promising allosteric inhibitor candidate for EGFR triple resistance mutations. These findings provide a rational foundation for further experimental validation and optimization in the development of next-generation EGFR inhibitors.

Keywords

allosteric inhibitor, EGFR, molecular dynamics, resistance mutations, virtual screening

Introduction

Cancer remains the second leading cause of death globally, following cardiovascular disease. Among all cancer-related deaths, lung cancer accounts for approximately one-third, with an estimated 1.38 million deaths annually worldwide (Bray et al. 2018). According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), there were approximately 1.8 million new cases of lung cancer in 2012, representing 12.9% of all cancer diagnoses, 58% of which occurred in less-developed regions (Wild 2014). Lung cancer remains the most common cancer in men, with an estimated 1.2 million cases (16.7% of all cancers in men) reported in 2012 (Gridelli et al. 2015).

Lung cancer is classified into two main types: small cell lung cancer (SCLC), accounting for approximately 20% of cases, and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), which represents the remaining 80%. Unfortunately, only approximately 15% of patients survive beyond 5 years after diagnosis (Cooper et al. 2022). Epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase (EGFR-TK) plays an important role in cell differentiation and proliferation under normal physiological conditions and in cancer (Giaccone and He 2023). Mutations in the EGFR gene were the first oncogenic drivers identified in NSCLC, making them key therapeutic targets for EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) (Maemondo 2016). The most prominent mutations found in patients receiving TKI therapy are deletions in exon 19 and the L858R point mutation in exon 21. Together, these two types of mutations represent almost 90% of the mutations associated with increased drug sensitivity in NSCLC (Maemondo 2016; Byun et al. 2022).

Despite their initial efficacy, resistance to EGFR-TKI therapy often develops. One major resistance mechanism is the T790M mutation in exon 20, which diminishes the effectiveness of first-generation EGFR inhibitors such as erlotinib and gefitinib (He et al. 2021; Passaro et al. 2017). Second-generation EGFR inhibitors, such as afatinib, inhibit mutant and wild-type EGFR (WT), resulting in adverse effects and dose-limiting toxicities (Passaro et al. 2017; Wu and Lin 2022; Remon et al. 2023). Third-generation EGFR inhibitors have been developed and are currently undergoing clinical and preclinical trials (Remon et al. 2018). Third-generation EGFR-TKIs, including osimertinib, are designed to overcome T790M-mediated resistance by covalently binding to the C797 residue (Passaro et al. 2017; Remon et al. 2018, 2023; He et al. 2021). However, recent studies have shown that subsequent resistance has emerged through additional mutations, such as C797S, which prevent covalent binding and render these drugs ineffective (Saini et al. 2023; Haratake et al. 2024).

In 2016, Jia et al. identified the fourth-generation EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors EGFR Allosteric Inhibitor 001

(EAI001) and EGFR Allosteric Inhibitor 045 (EAI045), which were the first allosteric inhibitors targeting T790M- and C797S-mutant EGFR, which confers resistance to third-generation inhibitors (Jia et al. 2016; Wang et al. 2017). These compounds represent the first type of EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor to occupy the allosteric site of EGFR and bind noncompetitively (Jia et al. 2016). However, resistance mutations associated with third-generation EGFR-TKIs include not only the C797S mutation but also the L718Q mutation (Li et al. 2022). L718Q mutations have also been reported as one of the causes of resistance to third-generation EGFR-TKIs (Shen et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2022). The L858R/T790M/L718Q triple mutation in Ba/F3 cells results in a high IC_{50} value for third-generation inhibitors (Wang et al. 2022).

Importantly, L718Q mutations frequently arise as secondary mutations in tumors with pre-existing L858R alterations and directly interfere with osimertinib binding by inducing steric hindrance within the ATP-binding pocket. *In vitro* studies further demonstrated that the L858R/T790M/L718Q EGFR triple mutant exhibits markedly increased IC_{50} values for third-generation EGFR-TKIs, confirming its strong resistance phenotype (Wang et al. 2024). Although recent advances in allosteric EGFR inhibition, such as the development of JBJ-09-063, have shown promising activity against multiple therapy-resistant EGFR mutants, including T790M and C797S, these agents have not been systematically evaluated against exon 18 resistance mutations such as L718Q. This finding highlights a critical gap in current EGFR drug development because most allosteric inhibitors have been optimized primarily for T790M- or C797S-driven resistance (To et al. 2022). Recent structure-based virtual screening (SBVS) and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation studies have demonstrated the feasibility of identifying novel allosteric EGFR inhibitors with diverse chemical scaffolds and favorable selectivity profiles. However, existing computational efforts have predominantly focused on T790M-containing EGFR mutants, whereas resistance-conferring mutations that directly impair osimertinib binding—such as L718Q—remain underexplored at the structural and molecular levels (Çoban 2024).

Developing new EGFR inhibitors through experimental methods can be time-consuming and costly. Therefore, this study employs an *in silico* approach using homology modeling to construct EGFR triple-mutant structures (Nurisyah et al. 2024) and pharmacophore-guided virtual screening (VS) to identify potential inhibitors. Pharmacophores represent the spatial arrangement of key molecular features—such as hydrogen-bond donors and acceptors, hydrophobic groups, and metal ligands—required for op-

timal interactions with biological targets (Hikmawati et al. 2022). This study aims to construct a robust pharmacophore model based on known allosteric EGFR inhibitors and to identify novel compounds capable of effectively targeting EGFR harboring the L858R/T790M/L718Q mutations. By specifically addressing the underexplored L718Q resistance mutation, this work seeks to contribute to the rational design of next-generation allosteric EGFR inhibitors to overcome osimertinib resistance in NSCLC.

Materials and methods

Protein preparation and mutagenesis

The template wild-type EGFR structure (WT; PDB code 5D41) was downloaded from the Protein Data Bank (Burley et al. 2019). The structure was prepared by removing heteroatoms, including water molecules, ions, and ligands, that were not relevant to the docking procedure. Mutagenesis was performed using PyMOL to introduce the L718Q mutation into the EGFR kinase domain (Nurisyah et al. 2024). The mutation was introduced by substituting the hydrophobic Leu718 residue with the polar residue Gln, which is located near the allosteric binding pocket, to investigate its potential effects on the interactions between EGFR and inhibitors. Subsequently, energy minimization of the template and mutant EGFR structures was performed using YASARA Structure according to the default YASARA protocol. The structures were cleaned, side-chain rotamers were optimized, hydrogen bonds were refined, and protonation states were adjusted to pH 7.4. Minimization was performed using steepest descent followed by simulated annealing until convergence, defined as an energy improvement of less than 0.05 kJ mol⁻¹ per atom. The optimized structures were subsequently used for further computational analyses (Land and Humble 2018; Bhandari et al. 2024).

Evaluation and optimization of protein structures

Evaluation was performed using the MolProbity and Verify3D web servers to assess the stereochemical quality and spatial properties of the constructed models. The parameters included the percentage of residues with an average 3D–1D score ≥ 0.2 , the MolProbity score, and the Ramachandran plot. The template and mutant proteins were then evaluated, and changes in their active sites related to allosteric inhibitor binding were compared.

Pharmacophore modeling and virtual screening

Pharmacophore models were developed using the allosteric inhibitors EAI001 and EAI045 as the training set, alongside decoys obtained from the ZINC database using DecoyFinder 2.0 (Cereto-Massagué et al. 2012). The de-

coy compounds were selected to ensure structural diversity while maintaining physicochemical relevance to the inhibitors. Training-set alignment was performed using the Flexible Alignment tool in the Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) (Group 2018). The best alignment model was selected based on its S score. The best pharmacophore model, which showed the highest sensitivity (Se = 1) and specificity (Sp = 0.92), was selected for virtual screening of the NCI Open Chemical Repository Database using Pharmit (Sunseri and Koes 2016). The compounds were filtered based on drug-likeness criteria using Lipinski's Rule of Five, Veber's criteria, and the number of aromatic nuclei. Subsequently, a total of 100 decoy compounds were prepared and retrieved from the ZINC database using DecoyFinder software. Suitable decoys were selected according to established criteria to ensure physicochemical similarity to the active compounds while maintaining structural dissimilarity (Irwin 2008). Specifically, candidate decoys were required to meet the following constraints: (i) molecular weight within ± 25 Da of the corresponding active compound; (ii) number of rotatable bonds within ± 1 ; (iii) number of hydrogen-bond donors within ± 1 ; (iv) number of hydrogen-bond acceptors within ± 2 ; (v) logP within ± 1 ; (vi) a Tanimoto coefficient ≤ 0.75 between each candidate decoy and the active compound; and (vii) a Tanimoto coefficient ≤ 0.9 between any pair of selected decoys. These criteria were applied to minimize bias while ensuring an appropriate balance between physicochemical similarity and topological diversity. To avoid overfitting and ensure the robustness of the pharmacophore model, validation was performed using an external dataset comprising active compounds and their corresponding decoys that were not included in pharmacophore model construction. Model performance was evaluated based on its ability to discriminate active compounds from decoys.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking of the screened hits was initially performed using Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) software, which applies a rigid-receptor and flexible-ligand procedure. A combination of placement algorithms and scoring functions was applied. To validate the docking protocol, the native allosteric ligand was redocked. Several combinations of placement methods and scoring functions were evaluated, and docking accuracy was assessed by calculating the root mean square deviation (RMSD) between the redocked ligand pose and its crystallographic conformation. The combinations of placement methods and scoring functions were validated, with the best combination showing an average RMSD of < 2.0 Å (Bell and Zhang 2019). This combination was used to dock the hits identified through pharmacophore screening. To further support the robustness of the docking results and minimize software-specific bias, an independent docking calculation was performed using AutoDock4 (Morris et al. 2009). The same docking grid coordinates, centered on the

native allosteric ligand-binding site, were applied to ensure consistency between the docking platforms. AutoDock4 simulations were conducted using the Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA), generating 100 docking conformations per ligand. The lowest-energy binding pose from the most populated cluster was selected for analysis (Morris et al. 2009). Compounds that were consistently ranked favorably using both docking approaches were considered more reliable candidates and were selected for further analysis.

Toxicological screening

To assess the safety profiles of the identified compounds, their carcinogenicity, hepatotoxicity, human ether-à-go-go-related gene (hERG) channel blockade potential, and mutagenicity were predicted using toxicity prediction models (Islam et al. 2020). These compounds were evaluated using mouse, rat, and *in silico* models to assess their potential adverse effects. The toxicity data were compiled and analyzed to prioritize compounds with safer pharmacological profiles for further investigation. *In silico* toxicity prediction was conducted to evaluate the drug-likeness and safety profiles of the screened compounds before further development. Four key toxicity endpoints were selected: carcinogenicity in a rat model, mutagenicity, hERG channel blockade, and hepatotoxicity (HEPX), because these represent major determinants of late-stage drug attrition for small-molecule kinase inhibitors. Carcinogenicity and mutagenicity were assessed to estimate potential genotoxic and long-term safety risks, whereas hERG channel blockade was evaluated to predict cardiotoxic liability. Hepatotoxicity was included because of the liver's central role in drug metabolism and the known hepatic adverse effects associated with EGFR-targeted therapies. Collectively, these endpoints provided an early safety assessment for prioritizing compounds with a favorable efficacy-toxicity balance.

Molecular dynamics simulation

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed for the native ligand EAI001 and the lead compound identified through virtual screening in complexes with the template and mutant proteins. GROMACS software with AMBER force fields was used in this study (Smith et al. 2015; Lolok et al. 2024). The molecular dynamics simulation process began with the construction of protein and ligand topologies and parameters. Ligand topologies were constructed using the ACPYPE script (Sousa da Silva and Vranken 2012). The solvation process was then performed using the TIP3P water model (Mark and Nilsson 2001; Smith et al. 2015), followed by the addition of counterions (Na⁺ and Cl⁻). Furthermore, the protein structure was minimized using the Amber99SB-ILDN force field (Ren et al. 2020). The system was then equilibrated for temperature at 310 K for 250 ps using a velocity-rescaling thermostat (Tiburu et al. 2018) and for pressure at 1 bar for 250 ps (Tiburu et al. 2018). Molecular dynamics simulations

were performed for 100 ns for each complex. The molecular dynamics simulation results were evaluated based on backbone RMSD, backbone root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), and hydrogen-bond conditions based on their percentage occupancy values. For the molecular mechanics/Poisson–Boltzmann surface area (MM/PBSA) calculations, the *g_mmpbsa* package in GROMACS 2016.3 was used (Ren et al. 2020). Data from 100 snapshots, which were collected at 10-s intervals and covered the MD trajectory from 0 to 100 ns, were averaged for the energy calculations (Hikmawati et al. 2022). The polar desolvation energy was determined by applying the Poisson–Boltzmann equation with a grid size of 0.5 Å (Swanson et al. 2004). The dielectric constant of the solvent was set to 80, representing water. The nonpolar energy contribution was assessed by calculating the solvent-accessible surface area using a solvent radius of 1.4 Å. An in-depth evaluation of the protein–ligand binding free energy was conducted. The MM/PBSA calculations were performed using the following equations:

$$\Delta G_{\text{bind}} = \Delta E_{\text{MM}} + \Delta G_{\text{solv}} - T\Delta S$$

$$\Delta E_{\text{MM}} = \Delta E_{\text{int}} + \Delta E_{\text{ele}} + \Delta E_{\text{vdw}}$$

$$\Delta G_{\text{solv}} = \Delta G_{\text{PB}} + \Delta G_{\text{SA}}$$

Results

EGFR mutant modeling and evaluation of its binding

The template EGFR structure with PDB code 5D41 was successfully modified through an *in silico* mutagenesis process to introduce the L718Q mutation. This substitution was introduced within the kinase domain at the Leu718 residue, which is situated near the allosteric binding pocket (Table 1).

The mutant protein was subsequently evaluated. The evaluation was performed before and after energy minimization and covered the spatial and stereochemical properties of the generated protein model. The MolProbity server was used to assess the Ramachandran plot, clashscore, and MolProbity score, whereas the Verify3D server was used to evaluate the Verify3D score. The Ramachandran plot describes the distribution of amino acid residues in the protein model structure. The assessment is based on the percentage of residues located in the most favored regions and also identifies disallowed regions for all amino acids except glycine. The Ramachandran outlier value indicates the number of residues located in unfavorable regions; therefore, lower values indicate a higher-quality model. The clashscore represents the number of steric overlaps per 1,000 atoms, with lower values indicating a better model. The MolProbity score is a composite metric that combines the clashscore and the percentage of poor rotamers, reflecting the equivalent crystallographic resolution of the model.

Table 1. List of the template and mutant sequences used for modeling (point mutations marked in bold).

Protein	Sequence
Template protein (5D41) (T790M/V948R)	GSTSGEAPNQALLRILKETEFKKIKVLGSGAFGTVYKGLWIPEGEKVKIPVAIK ELREATSPKANKEILDEAYVMASVDNPHVCRLLGICLTSTVQLIMQLMPFGCLL DYVREHKDNIGSQYLLNWCVQIAKGMNYLEDRLVHRDLAARNVLVKTPQHVKI TDFGLAKLLGAEKEYHAEGGKVPKWMALLESILHRIYTHQSDVWSYGVTVWEL MTFGSKPYDGIPASEISSILEKGERLPQPPICTIDVYMIMRKCWMIDADSRPKF RELIIEFSKMARDPQRYLVIQGDERMHLPSPTDSNFYRALMDEEDMDDVDDADE YLIPQQG
Mutant (L858R/T790M/L718Q)	GSTSGEAPNQALLRILKETEFKKIKV Q SGAFGTVYKGLWIPEGEKVKIPVAIK ELREATSPKANKEILDEAYVMASVDNPHVCRLLGICLTSTVQLIMQLMPFGCLL DYVREHKDNIGSQYLLNWCVQIAKGMNYLEDRLVHRDLAARNVLVKTPQHVKI TDF G RAKLLGAEKEYHAEGGKVPKWMALLESILHRIYTHQSDVWSYGVTVWEL MTFGSKPYDGIPASEISSILEKGERLPQPPICTIDVYMIMRKCWMIDADSRPKF RELIIEFSKMARDPQRYLVIQGDERMHLPSPTDSNFYRALMDEEDMDDVDDADE YLIPQQG

Table 2. Evaluation results for the mutant protein model before and after energy minimization.

Protein	Ramachandran outlier	Clashscore	MolProbity score	Verify 3D score
Mutant	0.96%	8.84	1.85	90.82%
After minimization				
Mutant	0%	1.18	0.86	87.66%

Table 3. Summary of the binding energies and residue interactions of the allosteric inhibitor (native ligand) with the template and mutant proteins.

Proteins	Binding energy (Kcal/mol)	Specific hydrophobic interactions				Hydrogen bond	Total interacting residues
		Met790	Lys745	Leu777	Phe856		
Template	-11.31	+	+	+	+	Asp855	19
Mutant	-5.84	-	+	+	-	Arg858; Asp855; Lys754	15

The evaluation results are presented in Table 2. The Ramachandran outlier, clashscore, and MolProbity score indicated good model quality. After energy minimization, these scores further improved, indicating a higher-quality protein model.

Docking of the native ligand showed conformational changes that led to a decrease in its ability to bind to the allosteric site of the mutant protein harboring the L718Q mutation. The L858R/T790M/L718Q mutant had a binding energy of -5.84 kcal/mol, compared with -11.31 kcal/mol for the template protein. In the mutant protein, the native ligand formed more hydrogen bonds than in the template protein. Hydrogen bonds were formed with the Asp855, Lys745, and Arg858 residues. The presence of L718Q in the EGFR mutant caused a decrease in allosteric inhibitor activity. Allosteric inhibitor activity did not appear to be strongly affected by hydrogen bonding. The activity appeared to improve because of the greater number of other interactions, such as hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions (Table 3). The substitution of Leu (hydrophobic) with Gln (polar) resulted in a change in the chemical properties of the residue, which was predicted to affect ligand interactions and local stability based on the native ligand redocking results shown in Figs 1, 2 and Table 3.

The more evident conformational changes in the allosteric inhibitor in the mutant model are shown in Fig. 2. The position of the aminothiazole group in the native ligand changed by more than 90° in the mutant protein. In the mutant protein, the aminothiazole group remained in the upper position and interacted with the Met790 and Lys745 residues, although the interactions differed. The aminothiazole group of the native ligand in the template protein was positioned between the Met790 and Lys745 residues. The position of the aminothiazole group of the native ligand in the mutant protein shifted slightly, and the phenyl group also exhibited a different conformational orientation.

The mutant protein model was subsequently superimposed on the template protein to examine the conformation of the native ligand-binding site in their cocrystal forms. Visualization of the allosteric binding site confirmed the occurrence of steric clashes between the side chain of Met790 and the native ligand, the EGFR allosteric inhibitor EAI001, in the mutant protein. The superimposition of the mutant complex on the template protein complex is shown in Fig. 3. The direct interaction between the aminothiazole moiety of the allosteric inhibitor and Met790 has been reported as the primary factor contributing to the selectivity of fourth-generation EGFR inhibitors toward the T790M

Figure 1. Two-dimensional interactions of the native ligand (the allosteric inhibitor EAI001) with the **a.** template protein and **b.** mutant protein.

Figure 2. Three-dimensional poses of the allosteric inhibitor with the lowest binding energy obtained through molecular docking with the **a.** template protein and **b.** mutant protein.

Figure 3. Superimposition of the modeled mutant complex (red) on the template protein complex (yellow) and visualization of allosteric inhibitor binding.

resistance mutation. In contrast, in the mutant model used in this study, a steric clash occurred between the aminothiazole group of the allosteric inhibitor and Met790, leading to an alteration in ligand conformation. This analysis was consistent with the docking results shown in Fig. 2 and ultimately indicated a reduction in binding affinity and conformational changes in the allosteric inhibitor.

Pharmacophore-based virtual screening

The allosteric inhibitors EAI001 and EAI045 were used as the training set, and a total of 100 decoys were obtained based on the structures of the training-set compounds. The decoys were obtained from the ZINC database. Alignment of the training set was performed using the Flexible Alignment tool in MOE. The best alignment result, with an S score of -133.3362 , was obtained and used to identify the pharmacophore features. Seven pharmacophore features with a 100% feature score were obtained based on the results of the Pharmacophore Consensus analysis: F1 (aromatic ring center), F2 (hydrophobic region), F3 (metal ligator), F4&ML (hydrogen-bond acceptor and metal ligator), F5 (hydrogen-bond donor), F6&ML2 (hydrogen-bond acceptor and metal ligator 2), and F7&ML3 (hydrogen-bond acceptor and metal ligator 3). The features were then combined into seven models. Each model was validated by measuring its sensitivity and specificity. The feature combinations and validation results are provided in Table 4.

Based on the validation results, Model 4 performed much better than the other models in terms of sensitivity ($Se = 1$) and specificity ($Sp = 0.92$). This allowed pharmacophore searching or screening using Model 4 to identify compounds with characteristics similar to those of the allosteric inhibitors. The pharmacophore features of Model 4 can be seen in Fig. 4. The pharmacophore model in this study was constructed based on two structurally characterized allosteric EGFR inhibitors, EAI001 and EAI045, which represent the limited number of experimentally validated ligands available for the EGFR allosteric binding site. Consequently, the resulting pharmacophore should be regarded as a hypothesis-driven model aimed at capturing key interaction features within the allosteric pocket rather than as a broadly generalizable predictive model. The use of a very small number of active compounds may introduce potential bias and limit the robustness and generalizability of the pharmacophore model. Therefore, the

Figure 4. Pharmacophore features represented by Model 4.

reported sensitivity and specificity values should be interpreted with caution and are intended to provide an initial assessment of model performance rather than definitive predictive accuracy.

Screening was then conducted using the NCI Open Chemical Repository Database integrated into Pharmit. The database contains 144,104 compounds. Screening of the database was based on pharmacophore Model 4. Additional drug-likeness filters available in Pharmit were applied. Drug-likeness was determined based on three criteria: Lipinski's Rule of Five, Veber's criteria, and the number of aromatic nuclei (Sunseri and Koes 2016). The screening process yielded 1,628 hit compounds that met the criteria.

Virtual screening, molecular docking, and toxicity prediction

Following pharmacophore-based virtual screening, molecular docking was performed to prioritize potential allosteric inhibitors against EGFR. Before docking, the docking protocol was validated using 16 combinations of placement methods and scoring functions available in MOE (Table 5). Among the evaluated protocols, the combination of Alpha PMI placement and Affinity dG scoring yielded the lowest RMSD value (1.778 \AA), which was below the commonly accepted threshold of 2.0 \AA . This result indicated that the selected protocol was capable of reproducing the reference ligand-binding pose with acceptable accuracy and was therefore considered suitable for virtual screening.

Table 4. Combinations of features and validation of the pharmacophore models.

Model	Combination of features	The number of training sets detected	The number of decoys detected	Sensitivity (Se)	Specificity (Sp)
Model 1	F1 – F2 – F3 – F4 – F5 – F6	0/2	0/100	0	0
Model 2	F1 – F2 – F3 – F4 – F5 – F7	0/2	0/100	0	0
Model 3	F1 – F2 – F3 – F5 – F6 – F7	0/2	8/100	0	0
Model 4	F1 – F2 – F4 – F5 – F6 – F7	2/2	1/100	1	0.92
Model 5	F1 – F3 – F4 – F5 – F6 – F7	0/2	35/100	0	0.65
Model 6	F2 – F3 – F4 – F5 – F6 – F7	0/2	0/100	0	0
Model 7	F1 – F2 – F3 – F4 – F5 – F6 – F7	0/2	0/100	0	0

Table 5. Redocking validation by combining placement methods and scoring functions using MOE software.

Placement scoring	Scoring function			
	Affinity dG	Alpha HB	ASE	London dG
Alpha PMI	1.7780	3.0489	4.1552	2.1478
Alpha Triangle	4.6688	4.5630	4.8723	4.8104
Proxy Triangle	4.8389	4.4956	4.8439	4.7636
Triangle Matcher	4.8389	4.4956	4.8439	4.7636

Using the validated docking protocol, a total of 1,628 compounds obtained from pharmacophore screening were docked into the allosteric binding site. The compounds were ranked according to their docking scores and binding poses, and 14 compounds exhibiting favorable interaction profiles within the allosteric pocket were selected for further evaluation (Table 6). The MOE docking scores of these compounds ranged from -8.48 to -6.99 kcal/mol, whereas the native ligand exhibited a docking score of -11.33 kcal/mol. Although the selected compounds showed less favorable docking scores than the native ligand, they demonstrated acceptable binding orientations and interactions with key residues in the allosteric binding site and were therefore subjected to further analysis using AutoDock4 and toxicity prediction.

The selected compounds were subsequently docked against both the EGFR template structure and the EGFR triple-mutant model (L858R/T790M/L718Q) using AutoDock4. The resulting binding energies are summarized in Table 7. Several compounds exhibited stronger binding affinities than the native ligand toward either the template or mutant protein. In the template structure, NSC10 showed the most favorable binding energy (-12.01 kcal/mol), followed by NSC1 (-11.89 kcal/mol), NSC3 (-11.86 kcal/mol), and NSC8 (-11.86 kcal/mol), all of which demonstrated stronger predicted binding than the native ligand (-11.33 kcal/mol). For the mutant protein, NSC4 displayed the strongest binding affinity (-8.73 kcal/mol), followed by NSC3 (-8.23 kcal/mol), NSC14 (-8.14 kcal/mol), and NSC10 (-7.86 kcal/mol), substantially outperforming the native ligand (-5.84 kcal/mol).

Among the screened compounds, NSC3 exhibited the most balanced binding profile toward both protein systems, with binding energies of -11.86 kcal/mol against the template structure and -8.23 kcal/mol against the mutant protein. Compared with the native ligand, NSC3 maintained comparable affinity toward the template receptor while displaying substantially stronger binding toward the mutant protein. These findings suggest that NSC3 possesses favorable binding characteristics for inhibiting both template and resistant EGFR forms and therefore represents a promising lead compound for further investigation.

Toxicity prediction using ADMET Predictor revealed that most compounds were predicted to be noncarcinogenic. Only NSC13 showed carcinogenic potential in mouse-based predictions, whereas NSC4 was predicted to be carcinogenic in rat-based predictions. Several compounds, including NSC1, NSC2, NSC6, NSC7, NSC10,

Table 6. Structures and binding energy scores of hit compounds with the best binding poses to the template protein (5D41) using MOE software.

No.	Structure	Binding energy scores
Native ligand (Reference)		
		-11.33
1		-8.4825
2		-8.0553
3		-7.5708
4		-7.5342
5		-7.3663
6		-7.2882
7		-7.2672

No.	Structure	Binding energy scores
8		-7.2544
9		-7.1942
10		-7.1690
11		-7.0824
12		-7.0246
13		-7.0154
14		-6.9913

NSC12, NSC13, and NSC14, were predicted to exhibit hepatotoxic potential. In addition, NSC1, NSC6, NSC8, and NSC11 were predicted to block hERG channels, indicating possible cardiotoxic liabilities. Potential mutagenicity was predicted for NSC3, NSC6, NSC10, NSC11, and NSC13.

Interestingly, only NSC5 and NSC9 were predicted to be free of all evaluated toxicity endpoints. However, their binding affinities were less favorable than those observed for NSC3. NSC5 exhibited weaker binding energies than the native ligand toward both the template and mutant proteins, whereas NSC9 showed only a modest improvement relative to the native ligand against the mutant protein and did not outperform the native ligand in the template structure. Therefore, despite its predicted mutagenicity, NSC3 was selected as the lead compound because it provided the best overall balance between binding affinity toward both EGFR systems and predicted safety. Nevertheless, further experimental studies are required to validate its biological activity and toxicological profile.

Molecular dynamics simulation

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were carried out on native ligand complexes with the template and mutant proteins. In addition, simulations were carried out on the best screening compound, namely, NSC3. Complex stability based on the simulations was analyzed using backbone RMSD, backbone RMSE, percentage hydrogen-bond occupancy, and MM/PBSA binding energy calculations.

The backbone RMSD plot against time was generated to describe the stability of the complexes over the 100 ns simulation period, as shown in Fig. 5. Four complexes were analyzed: the native ligand–template complex, NSC3–template complex, native ligand–mutant complex, and NSC3–mutant complex. The native ligand–template complex exhibited the most stable behavior throughout the simulation, with RMSD values remaining consistently low, within the range of approximately 0.18–0.28 Å, indicating a well-equilibrated and structurally stable complex. Similarly, the NSC3–template complex showed comparable stability, maintaining RMSD values of approximately 0.22–0.35 Å after the initial equilibration phase, suggesting that NSC3 did not induce significant conformational perturbations in the template protein. In contrast, the native ligand–mutant complex demonstrated noticeable instability. After approximately 25–30 ns, the RMSD increased and fluctuated more strongly, reaching values of 0.30–0.37 Å, and remained relatively unstable until the end of the simulation. This behavior indicated reduced structural compatibility of the native ligand with the mutant protein and suggested weakened binding stability following mutation.

Interestingly, the NSC3–mutant complex showed initial fluctuations during the early simulation phase (0–25 ns), with RMSD values transiently exceeding 0.30 Å. However, after approximately 30 ns, the system gradually stabilized and maintained RMSD values within the range of 0.35–0.45 Å for up to 100 ns. Although the RMSD values were slightly higher than those observed in the template complexes, the overall trend indicated that NSC3 was able to adapt to the mutant binding pocket and form a relatively stable complex at the allosteric site over the 100 ns simulation period.

Table 7. Binding energies of the native ligand and hit compounds with the mutant and template proteins using AutoDock4, along with a summary of their toxicity predictions using ADMET Predictor.

Compounds code	Binding energy in mutant	Binding energy in template	Toxicity predictions				
			Carcinogenicity in mice	Carcinogenicity in rat	Mutantgenicity	hERG channel blockade	Hepatotoxicity (HEPX)
Native lig.	-5.84	-11.33	-	-	-	-	-
NSC1	-5.71	-11.89	No	No	No	Yes	Toxic
NSC2	-7.20	-10.00	No	No	No	No	Toxic
NSC3	-8.23	-11.86	No	No	Yes	No	Nontoxic
NSC4	-8.73	-9.92	No	Yes	No	No	Nontoxic
NSC5	-5.35	-7.61	No	No	No	No	Nontoxic
NSC6	-5.29	-11.63	No	No	Yes	Yes	Toxic
NSC7	-5.74	-10.16	No	No	No	No	Toxic
NSC8	-7.57	-11.86	No	No	No	Yes	Nontoxic
NSC9	-6.66	-10.73	No	No	No	No	Nontoxic
NSC10	-7.86	-12.01	No	No	Yes	No	Toxic
NSC11	-6.92	-8.03	No	No	Yes	Yes	Nontoxic
NSC12	-6.96	-9.74	No	No	No	No	Toxic
NSC13	-7.50	-11.40	Yes	No	Yes	No	Toxic
NSC14	-8.14	-11.43	No	No	No	No	Toxic

Figure 5. Graph of backbone RMSD versus time for the native ligand and NSC3 in complexes with the template and mutant proteins.

The fluctuations of amino acids, particularly the important residues at the allosteric site—Lys745, Met790, and Asp855—were analyzed for each complex based on backbone RMSF, as shown in Fig. 6. Fluctuations in the amino acid residues of each complex generally showed similar tendencies, particularly for the important residues. The flexibility of the Lys745 residue in the native ligand–template complex tended to be lower, with an RMSF value below 0.1 nm, than that in the native ligand–mutant complex, which had a value above 0.1 nm. The NSC3 complexes showed flexibility at specific residues that tended to be similar to the flexibility observed for the native ligand and NSC3 in the template proteins. Furthermore, the percentage hydrogen-bond occupancy from the simulations of the protein complexes was calculated based on a cutoff distance of $< 3.5 \text{ \AA}$ and a bond angle of $> 120^\circ$ to provide an overview of the quality of the hydrogen bonds occurring in each complex system (Table 8). Based on the percentage occupancy, the hydrogen bonds were divided into three types: very weak hydrogen

Figure 6. Graph of backbone RMSF versus residues for complexes of the native ligand and NSC3 with the template and mutant proteins during the 50 ns simulation.

bonds (25–50%), strong hydrogen bonds (50–75%), and very strong hydrogen bonds (75–100%). Therefore, the analysis focused primarily on the very strong hydrogen bonds that were formed. During the simulation, the native ligand–template complex produced a very strong hydrogen bond with the Lys745 residue, with an occupancy of 96.15%. The NSC3–template complex also produced a very strong hydrogen bond with Lys745, as indicated by an occupancy of 83.89%. Furthermore, the complexes with the mutant protein showed changes in hydrogen-bond occupancy. The native ligand still formed a hydrogen bond with Lys745, but its percentage occupancy decreased to 78.39%. However, the NSC3–mutant complex formed a very strong hydrogen bond with a different residue, namely, Thr854, with an occupancy of 86.81%. The total numbers of hydrogen bonds formed in the native ligand–template, NSC3–template, native ligand–mutant, and NSC3–mutant complexes were 252, 191, 233, and 370, respectively.

Table 8. Percentage hydrogen-bond occupancy of the ligand–protein complexes.

Proteins	Ligands	Donor	Acceptor	Percent hbond occupancy	Total hbond
Template	Native ligand	LYS745-Side-NZ	57N1014-Side-O08	96.15%	252
		57N1014-Side-N12	ASP855-Side-OD2	51.54%	
	NSC3	LYS745-Side-CD	nsc1014-Main-O	56.42%	191
		LYS745-Side-NZ	nsc1014-Main-O	83.89%	
Mutant	Native ligand	LYS745-Side-NZ	57N1014-Side-O08	78.39%	233
	NSC3	THR854-Side-OG1	nsc1014-Main-O	86.81%	370

MM/PBSA calculation

The MM/PBSA binding free energy calculations for the native ligand and NSC3 complexes with the template and mutant proteins are presented in Table 9. For the template protein, the native ligand–template complex showed the most favorable total binding free energy (-133.25 ± 13.34 kJ/mol), with major contributions from van der Waals (-221.20 ± 11.68 kJ/mol) and electrostatic interactions (-84.84 ± 8.09 kJ/mol). The NSC3–template complex exhibited a higher total binding free energy (-95.79 ± 72.62 kJ/mol), accompanied by reduced van der Waals and electrostatic contributions and larger fluctuations. In the mutant protein, the total binding free energy of the native ligand–mutant complex was -91.68 ± 36.06 kJ/mol, showing weaker van der Waals interactions than the template system. The NSC3–mutant complex displayed a comparable total binding free energy of -92.59 ± 50.07 kJ/mol. In this system, NSC3 showed a relatively stronger electrostatic contribution (-77.06 ± 33.01 kJ/mol) than the native ligand–mutant complex.

Discussion

In this study, a detailed virtual screening process was employed to identify potential inhibitors of EGFR with the triple resistance mutations L858R/T790M/L718Q. The successful modification of the template EGFR structure (PDB code 5D41) to produce the L718Q mutant provided a robust model for screening, and the incorporation of pharmacophore modeling, followed by molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations, allowed for an extensive evaluation of binding stability. The pharmacophore model built from the allosteric inhibitors EAI001 and EAI045, along with the decoy database, proved to be a highly effective approach for identifying compounds that

could interact with the allosteric binding site of EGFR. Model 4, which showed the best performance, with a sensitivity (Se) of 1 and a specificity (Sp) of 0.92, was chosen as the optimal model for further screening. This model effectively captured the critical features required for binding at the allosteric site, such as aromatic ring centers, hydrophobic regions, metal ligands, and hydrogen-bond acceptors. The high specificity and sensitivity of this pharmacophore model suggest its applicability for screening large compound databases for compounds with characteristics similar to those of the allosteric inhibitors (Yan et al. 2020).

Screening of the NCI Open Chemical Repository Database (144,104 compounds) using Model 4 yielded 1,628 hits, which were then subjected to further analysis. The addition of drug-likeness filters based on Lipinski's Rule of Five, Veber's criteria, and the aromatic nuclei count ensured that only the most promising compounds in terms of bioavailability and molecular properties (Wang et al. 2024) were selected for further evaluation. The molecular docking protocol involving MOE software was validated using a combination of the Affinity dG scoring function and Alpha PMI placement scoring, which resulted in an average RMSD of less than 2.0 Å. This low RMSD indicates that the docking protocol accurately reproduced the binding poses of known ligands, suggesting that it can be confidently used to screen novel compounds. The consensus scoring method, which incorporates multiple docking scores, has been widely reported to enhance the success rate of virtual screening, further validating the choice of protocol. After docking the 1,628 hits, 14 compounds were identified as having superior activity compared with the native ligand in the template protein. These compounds were selected for further docking with both the template and mutant EGFR proteins. Interestingly, compound 3 exhibited the best binding activity, with binding energies of -11.86 kcal/mol for the template and -8.23 kcal/mol for the mutant EGFR.

Table 9. MM/PBSA calculations for the native ligand and NSC3 in complexes with the template and mutant receptors.

Binding free energy calculations	Ligand-receptor complex			
	Native–template	NSC3–template	Native–mutant	NSC3–mutant
Van de waals energy (KJ/mol)	-221.199 ± 11.680	-205.667 ± 61.158	-180.136 ± 95.730	-167.05 ± 39.6
Electrostatic energy (KJ/mol)	-84.840 ± 8.093	-54.362 ± 19.222	-57.980 ± 31.805	-77.06 ± 33.01
Polar solvation energy (KJ/mol)	191.053 ± 11.444	185.315 ± 51.371	156.671 ± 73.001	$+168.18 \pm 43.76$
SASA energy (KJ/mol)	-18.261 ± 0.724	-16.964 ± 5.117	-14.349 ± 7.457	-16.57 ± 3.85
Total binding energy (KJ/mol)	-133.246 ± 13.335	-95.794 ± 72.617	-91.677 ± 36.055	-92.59 ± 50.070

In comparison, the native ligand had binding energies of -11.33 kcal/mol for the template and -5.84 kcal/mol for the mutant, suggesting that compound 3 could be a promising candidate for further development as an EGFR inhibitor targeting the triple resistance mutations.

The screening also incorporated toxicological assessments to evaluate the safety of the identified compounds. Notably, NSC13 was predicted to be carcinogenic in mouse models, whereas compound 4 showed potential carcinogenicity in rat testing. Furthermore, several compounds were flagged for potential hepatotoxicity, with NSC1, NSC2, NSC6, NSC7, NSC10, NSC12, NSC13, and NSC14 showing risks in this regard. Several compounds, including NSC1, NSC6, NSC8, and NSC11, were also identified as potential blockers of hERG channels, which is a critical factor in assessing the safety of drug candidates in relation to cardiac arrhythmias. In addition, several compounds, including NSC3, NSC6, NSC10, NSC11, and NSC13, were found to be mutagenic, further emphasizing the importance of evaluating the safety profiles of lead compounds before advancing them to clinical trials.

The MD simulations provided further insights into the dynamic stability of the top candidate, NSC3, compared with the native ligand. Both the NSC3–template and native ligand–template complexes showed stable binding, with RMSD values of 0.15 – 0.25 nm, whereas the NSC3–mutant complex initially fluctuated but stabilized after 27 ns, demonstrating adaptability to mutation-induced structural changes. In contrast, the native ligand–mutant complex remained unstable, with RMSD values reaching 0.37 nm. RMSF analysis revealed that the mutations increased the flexibility of critical residues, such as Lys745, in the native ligand–mutant complex, whereas NSC3 maintained flexibility patterns closer to those of the template-bound systems. Hydrogen-bond analysis confirmed the adaptability of NSC3: although the hydrogen-bond occupancy of the native ligand with Lys745 decreased in the mutant, NSC3 formed a strong alternative hydrogen bond with Thr854 (86.81%) and generated the highest total number of hydrogen bonds (370). The MM/PBSA analysis provides molecular insight into the stability trends observed in the 100 ns RMSD simulations. In the template protein, the native ligand showed the strongest binding affinity, driven primarily by favorable van der Waals and electrostatic interactions, which is consistent with the low and stable RMSD values observed throughout the simulation. The NSC3–template complex, although exhibiting slightly weaker binding energy, maintained structural stability comparable to that of the native ligand, indicating that NSC3 fits well within the native binding pocket. In the mutant protein, both ligands experienced a reduction in binding affinity, reflecting the structural and physicochemical changes induced by the mutation. The native ligand–mutant complex showed weaker van der Waals interactions and increased conformational fluctuations, in agreement with its higher RMSD values and reduced stability during the simulation. Interestingly, despite exhibiting higher RMSD values, the NSC3–mutant complex maintained a total binding

free energy comparable to that of the native ligand. This behavior suggests that NSC3 adapts to the altered binding environment by enhancing electrostatic interactions, which partially compensate for the loss of hydrophobic contacts. The increased flexibility observed in the RMSD profile may therefore reflect adaptive rearrangements rather than binding instability. The selection of only EAI001 and EAI045 for pharmacophore generation was based on their availability as cocrystallized ligands with the EGFR allosteric site and their well-established activity against mutant EGFR. These compounds represent the few known inhibitors that selectively target the allosteric binding pocket, thus serving as reliable templates for model generation. Despite the promising results, this study has several limitations. First, the pharmacophore model was derived from only two known active compounds, which may limit the diversity and generalizability of the screened hits. In addition, all validation was conducted *in silico*, including toxicity predictions and binding energy estimations. The predicted toxicity risks, including carcinogenicity and hERG inhibition, require experimental confirmation. Furthermore, although the triple-mutant EGFR model was generated based on existing structural data, the absence of a crystal structure for the complete L858R/T790M/L718Q mutant introduces potential uncertainty into the binding-site conformation. Overall, the combined approach demonstrates that NSC3 is a promising allosteric inhibitor candidate capable of overcoming mutation-induced resistance, but further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are essential to confirm both its efficacy and safety.

Conclusion

Based on homology modeling and molecular docking analyses, the L858R/T790M/L718Q triple mutation in EGFR was observed to induce conformational changes that may reduce the effectiveness of known allosteric inhibitors. Virtual screening of the NCI Open Chemical Repository Database yielded 14 hit compounds predicted to interact with the EGFR allosteric site and share key interaction features with established allosteric inhibitors. Among these candidates, NSC3 showed the most favorable docking performance against both the mutant and template EGFR structures.

Molecular dynamics simulations extended to 100 ns indicated that the NSC3–template complex exhibited stability comparable to that of the native ligand–template complex, whereas the NSC3–mutant complex demonstrated improved stability relative to the native ligand–mutant system. The simulation results suggest that NSC3 may accommodate mutation-induced conformational changes through alternative hydrogen-bonding patterns; however, these findings should be interpreted qualitatively because of the inherent limitations of docking scores and finite simulation times.

In silico toxicity predictions indicated potential safety liabilities, including hepatotoxicity, mutagenicity, and

hERG inhibition, for some of the screened compounds, underscoring the preliminary nature of these predictions. Overall, this computational study identifies NSC3 as a candidate of interest for further investigation as a

potential EGFR allosteric inhibitor. Nevertheless, experimental validation and structural optimization are required to confirm its biological activity, selectivity, and safety.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

The following AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript:

AI tools: ChatGPT.

Used for: Language, style and writing.

Description: ChatGPT was used to improve the language and readability of the manuscript. No images were generated or manipulated using AI tools.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
